

Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ Reversibility on Clay-membrane Electrodes in Aquo and Aquo-ethanolic Solvents

M. Adhikari

Mobility ratios of Ca and Mg ion pair on clay-membrane electrodes have been determined from E.M.F. measurements of cells constituted of membranes separating two solutions having known activities of Ca and Mg ions in aquo and aquo-ethanolic solvents. The values of the mobility ratio, which may be regarded as a correction term to the Nernst equation, remain fairly constant for particular membrane electrodes over the activity range used to evaluate them. The change of solvent does not practically show any change of mobility ratio for the same membrane electrode within the same range of activities. These membranes have also been used to measure the potential difference between solutions containing on one side a mixture of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions and on the other side Ca²⁺ ion and from the observed E.M.F., mobility ratio has been calculated. The agreement between mobility ratios from these two sets of experiments is satisfactory.

The use of clay-membrane electrodes for the cationic activity determination has been emphasised by Marshall¹, Chatterjee², and others³. These workers considered clay membrane as a cationic reversible electrode and showed the possibility of characterising the membrane by two quantities, viz., (i) the charge on the membrane surface and (ii) the 'mobility ratio' of the cations. Different cations are assumed to move with different speeds inside the membrane and hence the correction term, the mobility ratio, is introduced in the Nernst equation:

$$E = \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{a_{Ca^{2+}}}{a_{Mg^{2+}}} \cdot \frac{U_{Ca}}{U_{Mg}}$$

where U_{Ca}/U_{Mg} refers to 'mobility ratio'.

All these works were confined to aqueous solvents. The method of measuring individual ion activity by employing clay-membrane electrodes in aquo and aquo-organic solvents has been outlined in previous communications^{4,5}. The present investigation is concerned with calcium-magnesium reversibility, an evaluation of the 'mobility ratios' of the cations using different types of membranes, and determination of the activity of each of these ions in a mixture of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions in aquo and aquo-ethanolic solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental procedures were exactly the same as described earlier⁴. Only those membranes, which were found satisfactory in previous electrochemical studies, were employed

1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, 43, 1155; 1946, 52, 1284.
2. *This Journal, Ind. & News Ed.*, 1949, 12, 73.
3. Bose, *J. Ind. Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1955, 3, 5, 109.
4. Adhikari, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 373, 569.

in the present investigation. From the observed E.M.F. for the cell arrangement of the type:

the mobility ratio is calculated from the relationship:

$$E_{\text{obs}} = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}}{a_{\text{Mg}^{2+}}} \cdot \frac{U_{\text{Cl}^-}}{U_{\text{Mg}}} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{\text{Cl}^-}}{a_{\text{Cl}^-}}$$

The calculated mobility ratios of different electrodes in aqueous solutions are recorded in Table I. For activities of cations in aquo-organic solvents, these data were calculated as reported previously⁴. The calculated mobility ratios in aquo-ethanolic solutions are shown in Table II.

TABLE I

Ca, Mg in aqueous soln.

Temp. = 25°. Observed E.M.F. in m.v., outside + ve observed.

Membrane.	Inside Ca ²⁺ = 0.0009 Outside Mg ²⁺ = 0.0009			= 0.0027 = 0.0027		
	Obs. E.M.F.	E.M.F. for Cl ⁻ /Cl ⁻ .	$\frac{U_{\text{Ca}}}{U_{\text{Mg}}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	E.M.F. for Cl ⁻ /Cl ⁻ .	$\frac{U_{\text{Ca}}}{U_{\text{Mg}}}$
Padegaon Ca-form	1.0	Nil	1.0	4.7	1.8	1.05
„ Na-form	1.0	Nil	1.0	4.8	1.8	1.10
	Inside Ca ²⁺ = 0.0081 Outside Mg ²⁺ = 0.0081					
Padegaon Ca-form	3.7	3.0	1.0	..	..	..
„ Na-form	4.1	3.0	1.1	..	..	..

TABLE II

Membrane.	Inside Ca ²⁺ = 0.000724 Outside Mg ²⁺ = 0.000821			= 0.0018 = 0.0019		
	Obs. E.M.F.	E.M.F. for Cl ⁻ /Cl ⁻ .	$\frac{U_{\text{Ca}}}{U_{\text{Mg}}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	E.M.F. for Cl ⁻ /Cl ⁻ .	$\frac{U_{\text{Ca}}}{U_{\text{Mg}}}$
	A. Ca, Mg in 50% aquo-ethanolic solution.					
Padegaon Ca-form	0.95	Nil	1.0	4.8	1.8	1.10
„ Na-form	0.95	Nil	1.0	5.0	1.8	1.15
	Inside Ca ²⁺ = 0.00412 Outside Mg ²⁺ = 0.00470					
Padegaon Ca-form	5.0	3.6	1.1	..	..	..
„ Na-form	4.9	3.6	1.1	..	..	..

TABLE II (contd.)

B. Ca, Mg in 25% water and 75% ethanol.

Membrane.	$\frac{\text{Inside Ca}^{2+}}{\text{Outside Mg}^{2+}} = \frac{0.000652}{0.000558}$			$= \frac{0.00110}{0.00124}$		
	Obs. E.M.F.	E.M.F. for Cl ⁻ /Cl ⁻ .	$\frac{U_{Ca}}{U_{Mg}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	E.M.F. for Cl ⁻ /Cl ⁻ .	$\frac{U_{Ca}}{U_{Mg}}$
Pedegaon Ca-form	0.9	Nil	1.0	2.8	1.3	1.1
„ Na-form	0.9	Nil	1.0	2.9	1.3	1.1
	$\frac{\text{Inside Ca}^{2+}}{\text{Outside Mg}^{2+}} = \frac{0.00178}{0.00240}$					
Pedegaon Ca-form	3.5	3.3	1.1	..	..	..
„ Na-form	3.5	3.3	1.1	..	..	..

DISCUSSION

Except for the slight irregular variation of the mobility ratios with activities of the ions, these may be regarded as constant, as expected. With the change of solvents, hence of dielectric constant, the mobility ratio has not changed appreciably. On applying these values of mobility ratios for measurements of unknown activities, it is found expedient to use as far as possible the exact mobility ratio in the particular activity range in which it has been evaluated, instead of using an average value. The constant mobility ratio, which is obtained in the present case, will have its importance from the practical point of view.

Determination of Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ ion Activities in a Mixture of the Two.—As already explained, the mobility ratio acts, as it were, as a correction term in the Nernst equation. It probably arises from the difference in the speed of the ions inside a permeable membrane or in the exchangeability of the ions on the electrode surface. In a mixture of two ions in solutions, e.g., Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, their relative effect on the electrode surface is assumed to be determined by their mobility ratio. U_{Ca}/U_{Mg} has been determined with the help of the equation²:

$$E_{\text{obs}} = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a_{Ca^{2+}}}{a_{Mg^{2+}} + a_{Ca^{2+}} \left(\frac{U_{Ca}}{U_{Mg}} \right)} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{Cl_1^-}}{a_{Cl_2^-}}$$

for a cell set-up of the type :

Results of such determinations in aqueous and aquo-ethanolic solvents are shown in Tables III and IV. The agreement of U_{Ca}/U_{Mg} values between these two sets of experiments suggests that the measurements of individual activities of ions in a mixture may be extended to unknown systems in aqueous and aquo-ethanolic solvents without any difficulty.

TABLE III

Ca, Mg in aqueous solutions.

Membrane.	Inside $\text{Ca}^{2+} = 0.0008, \text{Mg}^{2+} = 0.00088$ Outside $\text{Ca}^{2+} = 0.0009$			$\text{Ca}^{2+} = 0.0024, \text{Mg}^{2+} = 0.00243$ $\text{Ca}^{2+} = 0.0027$		
	Obs. E.M.F.	E.M.F. for Cl^-/Cl^- .	$\frac{U_{\text{Ca}}}{U_{\text{Mg}}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	E.M.F. for Cl^-/Cl^- .	$\frac{U_{\text{Ca}}}{U_{\text{Mg}}}$
Padegaon Ca-form	24.6	17.1	1.0	23.0	15.85	1.0
„ Na-form	24.7	17.1	1.0	22.5	15.85	0.90

TABLE IV

Membrane.	Inside $\text{Ca}^{2+} = 0.00061, \text{Mg}^{2+} = 0.00060$ Outside $\text{Ca}^{2+} = 0.000724$			$\text{Ca}^{2+} = 0.00148, \text{Mg}^{2+} = 0.00154$ $\text{Ca}^{2+} = 0.0018$		
	Obs. E.M.F.	E.M.F. for Cl^-/Cl^- .	$\frac{U_{\text{Ca}}}{U_{\text{Mg}}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	E.M.F. for Cl^-/Cl^- .	$\frac{U_{\text{Ca}}}{U_{\text{Mg}}}$
A. Ca, Mg in 50% aquo-ethanolic solution.						
Padegaon Ca-form	22.7	16.7	1.0	22.0	15.2	0.9
„ Na-form	22.7	16.7	1.0	21.5	15.2	0.9
B. Ca, Mg in 25% water and 75% ethanol.						
Inside $\text{Ca}^{2+} = 0.0004, \text{Mg}^{2+} = 0.000433$ Outside $\text{Ca}^{2+} = 0.00055$						
Padegaon Ca-form	21.5	16.2	1.0			
„ Na-form	21.8	16.2	1.0			

Author's thanks are due to Prof. S. K. Mukherjee, Dean of the Faculty of Science, University of Kalyani, for his helpful discussion and Dr. S. C. Niyogy, Head of the Department of Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University, for his encouragement.